

ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE OF RISK FACTORS OF HYPERTENSION AMONG GENERAL POPULATION OF NAWABSHAH

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Abstract

Background: Hypertension is linked with such risk factors like obesity, increase in the intake of salt, alcohol consumption and physical activity. Understanding and knowledge regarding its risk factors in individuals can enable to prevent and reduce the incidents.

Objective: This study aimed to assess the knowledge of risk factors of hypertension among the general population of Nawabshah.

Methodology: A cross sectional study was conducted at Peoples Medical College (PMCH) Nawabshah at Medical department from 17 November 2025 to 17 Jan 2026 with sample size 321, on the Individual aged >16years, both gender were included and individual willing to participate. Individual having psychiatric illness, age <16years and who decline to participate or refused to sign inform consent were excluded. The data collected through "Questionnaire" consisted of two sections: "SECTION A" demographic information, SECTION B" assessment of knowledge of risk factors of hypertension family history, eating unhealthy diet, stress, excessive consumption of alcohol, obesity, sedentary lifestyle, cigarette smoking after approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the Peoples University of Medical and Health Sciences Nawabshah. The Data analyzed by statistical package for science (SPSS) version 25. The descriptive statistics used for analyzing numerical data (frequencies and percentages).The participants ensured that their responses will be confidential during data collection and analysis.

Results: The result shows that the mean age of participants was 35.53 with SD \pm 12.15 was 306 (95.3%) were Muslims, the majority 203(63.4%) were Females, Most of the participants 227 (70.7%) belonged to Poor economic class, 209 (65.11) were Rural areas, most of the participants 251(78.2%) were Married, majority were 203 (63.68%) were Sindhi, 151 (47.33%) were Housewife, 171(53.27%) were Illiterate and 204 (63.6%) participants were lived in Joint family. Regarding the knowledge 66(20.56%) participants had Poor knowledge while 225(79.44%) had good knowledge. The majority of the

participants knew family history, 75.2% knew Eating unhealthy diet, 73.2% knew sedentary lifestyle, 52.6% Excessive consumption of alcohol, 54.21% knew Cigarette smoking ,68.8% knew obesity and 80.06% identified older age group is a risk factor of hypertension.

Conclusion: This study aim to assess the knowledge of risk factors of hypertension in general population of Nawabshah. The finding revealed that overall the majority of the 74.44% participants had good knowledge of hypertension. Different risk factors of hypertension's knowledge were assessed. The most commonly factors that knew majority of participants were 80.06% knew older age group, 75.7% knew Eating unhealthy diet, 73.2% knew stress, 68.54% Family history, 68.8% knew obesity, 62.62% knew Sedentary lifestyle, The least factors knew by the participants were 54.21% knew Cigarette smoking, 52.6% knew Excessive consumption of alcohol as risk factor of hypertension. The finding reveals that regarding the demographics status the majority of the participants were Females, Housewife, Muslims, Poor economic class, rural residence, Married, Sindhi, Illiterate and had live in joint family system.

INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is a leading public health issue that causes many health problems and death due to linked with cardiovascular diseases¹. It is a medical condition considered, when the reading of the blood pressure on repeatedly show measurement of systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg and diastolic blood pressure ≤ 90 mmHg². Hypertension sometime termed as high blood pressure that possess major health issue which effect the both developing and under developing countries³. World Health Organization (WHO) reports that yearly 7 million population involved with condition of hypertension⁴. Hypertension (HTN) is linked with such risk factors like obesity, increase in the intake of salt, alcohol consumption physical activity⁵. It affects the both kidney and brain of individual⁶. Also associated with many life threatening conditions like peripheral vascular disease, congestive heart failure, myocardial infarction and end stage renal disease⁷. Hypertension is asymptomatic so the majority of the peoples are not aware that they have such condition, raising the people's knowledge regarding its risk factors are a simple way to prevent from this condition⁸.

A non experimental descriptive design was conducted among non-health workers working in hospital results reveal that 53% respondents were aware that old age group is a risk factor for developing hypertension and 43% response that family history is a risk factor for hypertension⁹. Another cross-sectional study was conducted in

2021 at the St Augustine university of Tanzania concluded that majority of the participants perceived stress as a risk factor for hypertension and 58.5% identified that old age group, sedentary lifestyle, obesity and alcohol consumption as risk factors of hypertension¹⁰. A cross-sectional study conducted in the north and middle of Jordan results revealed that 32% participants were aware about alcohol consumption as risk factors of hypertension, about half of the participants were aware that family history is a risk factor of hypertension, and a large number of participants identified lack of physical activity, overweight and fatty foods are risk factors for hypertension¹¹. A retrospective study was conducted in rural community of Bangladesh results revealed that 77.9% participants strongly agreed that changing in lifestyle decrease risk of blood pressure and 79% of the participants disagreed that hypertension is an elderly disease¹². An analytical cross sectional study was conducted in Saudi Arabia between August 2022 and February 2023 results revealed that 72.8% correctly responds that hypertensive patient should not consume alcohol and 68.9% knew that hypertensive patient should not smoke¹³. A cross sectional study was conducted from November 2024 to February 2025 in the Departments of Medicine and Cardiology at Chaudhary Muhammad Akram Teaching and Research Hospital, Azra Naheed Medical College, Superior University, in Lahore, Pakistan result reveal that number of the

population has poor knowledge of hypertension about 53.3% participants knew that overweight increase the risk of hypertension, 58.3% identified that regular exercise decrease blood pressure¹⁴. Hypertension is a major health problem that leads an affective role in the quality of life of peoples overall the world. Understanding and knowledge, regarding its risk factors in individuals, can enable to prevent and reduce the incidents. There is a limited study conducted in Nawabshah population regarding the assessment of knowledge of risk factors of hypertension. Therefore, this study was conducted to assess the participant’s knowledge of risk factors of hypertension. The aim of this study was to assess the knowledge of risk factors of hypertension among the general population of Nawabshah.

METHODOLOGY

A Cross-sectional study was conducted at Peoples Medical College Hospital (PMCH) Nawabshah at Medicine department. This study was conducted from 17 November to 17 January (2 months) after approval from Institutional Review Board (IRB). The Sample size was 321 n calculated through Sample size calculation formula Level of significance = 0.05 Confidence interval = 95%. Non probability convenient sample technique was used to select the sample on those peoples who visited the medicine unit. The inclusion criteria were Individual aged > 16 years was included, individuals willing to participate and both gender were included. The individual having

psychiatric illness, aged <16 and declined to participate or refused to sign the informed consent was excluded from this study. The data was collected through “Questionnaire” from previous study consisted of two sections: “SECTION A” demographic information (Age, Gender, Residence, Religion, Ethnicity, Economic status, Marital status, Occupation, Educational status, Family status) and “SECTION B” assessment of knowledge of risk factors of hypertension which contains questions of risk factors, family history, eating unhealthy diet, stress, excessive consumption of alcohol, obesity, sedentary lifestyle, cigarette smoking. The participants chose “yes” or “no” to indicate whether the following factor is the risk factor for hypertension. The knowledge score ranged from 0 to 8. Participants obtained 1 point for each “yes” choosing option. 4 score = Good knowledge and < 4 = Poor knowledge. The collected Data analyzed by statistical package for science (SPSS) version 25.. The descriptive statistics were used for analyzing numerical data (frequencies and percentages) to describe the participant’s knowledge of hypertension’s risk factors. The Ethical considerations of this study were that the study was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the Peoples University of Medical and Health Sciences Nawabshah. The participants were ensured that their responses will be confidential during data collection and analysis. The consent form was obtained from each participant after explaining the purpose of study. No any sensitive information was collected from respondents.

RESULTS

Figure 1 Age of Participants.

Figure 2 Gender of Participants.

Table 1: Religion of the participants

Religion	Frequency	Percent%
Muslim	306	95.3%
Hindu	15	4.7%
Total	321	100.0%

Table 2: Economic status of participants

Economic class	Frequency	Percent%
Poor class	227	70.7%
Middle class	92	28.7%
High class	2	.6%
Total	321	100.0%

Figure 2: Residence of participants.

Figure 3: Ethnicity of participants

Table 3: Marital status of participants

Marital status	Frequency	Percent%
Single	69	21.5%
Married	251	78.2%
Divorced	1	.3%
Total	321	100.0

Table 4: Occupation of participants

Occupation	Frequency	Percent%
Farmer	55	17.1%
Carpenter	2	.6%
Housewife	151	47.0%
Others	113	35.2%
Total	321	100.0

Table 5: Family type of participants

Family type	Frequency	Percent
Single	112	34.9%
Joint	204	63.6%

Extended	5	1.6%
Total	321	100.0

Figure 4: Educational status

Figure 5: Knowledge of risk factor of hypertension

Table 6: Knowledge of risk factor of hypertension

Eating unhealthy diet is a risk factor for hypertension		
Qno:2	Frequency	Percent%
No	78	24.3%
Yes	243	75.7%
Total	321	100.0%

Table 7: Knowledge of risk factor of hypertension

Stress is a risk factor for hypertension		
Qno:3	Frequency	Percent%
No	86	26.8%
Yes	235	73.2%
Total	321	100.0%

Figure 6: Knowledge of risk factor of hypertension

Figure 7: Knowledge of risk factor of hypertension

Table 8: Knowledge of risk factor of hypertension

Excessive consumption of alcohol is a risk factor for hypertension		
	Frequency	Percent%
No	152	47.4%
Yes	169	52.6%
Total	321	100.0%

Table 9: Knowledge of risk factor of hypertension

Obesity is a risk factor for hypertension		
	Frequency	Percent%
No	97	30.2%
Yes	224	69.8%
Total	321	100.0%

Fig 8: Knowledge of risk factor of hypertension

Fig 9: Knowledge level of participants

DISCUSSION

Regarding the demographic variables of this study the results concluded the mean age of participants 35.53yrs with SD ±12.15, the previous study shows the mean age 40yrs SD±10.33. The majority of the participants 306 (95.3%) were Muslims when compared with the previous study the result shows that 61 (15.6%) participants were Muslims. The 36.76% participants were Male where as 63.24% were female, along that 70.7% participants economical status were Poor .Though when align with previous study the results stated that 65.8% were Female and 32.4% were Male and about the economic status 227 (26.6%) had Poor economic status. The 78.2% participants were Married, regarding their educational status results concludes majority of the participants 171 (53, 27%) were Illeterate while comparing this study with previous study results stated that 381 (52,7%) were Married and the less number of participants 8 (0.8%) were Illeterate. This study revealed that the majority 220 (68.54%) knew that “Family history is a risk factor for hypertension” while 243 (75.5%) had knowledge that “Eating unhealthy diet is a risk factor for hypertension. Comparing with previous study results concludes that 88.8% participants had knowledge that Family history is a risk factor for hypertension and 80.2% knew that Unhealthy diet is a risk factor for hypertension. 235 (73.2%) knew that Stress is a risk factor for hypertension and 201 (62.62%)

had knowledge that Sedentary life style is a risk factor for hypertension when compared with previous study the results concluded that 100% participants knew that Stress is a risk factor for hypertension 85% had knowledge that Sedentary life style is a risk factor for hypertension .169 (52.6%) knew that Alcohol consumption is a risk factor for hypertension and 54.41% had knowledge that Cigarette smoking is a risk factor for hypertension .When compared to the previous study found that only 141 (34.4%) participants identified that Consumption of Alcohol is a risk factors of hypertension. 69.8% participants knew that obesity is a risk factor for hypertension ,80.6% had knowledge that older age group is a risk factor for hypertension, compared to the previous study result revealed that 97.0% knew about obesity and 82.9% about Older age group as a risk factor. Over all 225 (79.44%) participants had Good level of knowledge, when align with previous study stated that only 68.52% had Good level of knowledge.

CONCLUSION

Hypertension is linked with various risk factors This study was conducted to assess the knowledge of risk factors of hypertension in general population of Nawabshah. The finding revealed that overall the majority of the 74.44% participants had good knowledge of hypertension. Different risk factors of hypertension’s knowledge were assessed. The

most commonly factors that knew majority of participants were: 80.06% knew older age group, 75.7% knew Eating unhealthy diet, 73.2% knew stress, 68.54% Family history, 68.8% knew obesity, 62.62% knew Sedentary lifestyle, The least factors knew by the participants were 54.21% knew Cigarette smoking, 52.6% knew Excessive consumption of alcohol as risk factor of hypertension. The finding reveals that regarding the demographics status the majority of the participants were Females, Housewife, Muslims, Poor economic class, Rural residence, Married, Sindhi, Illiterate and had live in joint family system.

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